

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF GINGIVAL RETRACTION USING VARIOUS METHODS

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ABSTRACT

In the manufacture of fixed orthopedic structures, gum retraction is one of the most important stages for obtaining a high-quality impression, since it is often necessary to work in the gingival and subgingival areas with significant tooth decay. The purpose of this manipulation is to retract the marginal gingiva to further display the boundaries of the preparation on the impression and working model.

Keywords: fixed denture structures, gum retraction using various methods.

The difficulty lies in the diversity of clinical conditions in each individual patient. For example, the type of mucosa of the patient, the presence of deep periodontal pockets, or, conversely, a shallow gingival sulcus, restorations are often made in the presence of significant subgingival destruction. In some cases, it is almost impossible to carry out high-quality retraction of the gingival margin. At the moment, there are many methods of gum retraction: mechanical gum retraction, in which various materials are introduced into the periodontal sulcus that move the gum away from the tooth (rings, the use of silicone caps, retraction using threads of various diameters), chemical gum retraction, when various chemical compounds are used with the effect of vasoconstrictors and hemostatic action (use of solutions, gels and pastes for retraction containing aluminum sulfate, epinephrine and others). However, the use of such drugs can cause exacerbation of various diseases, such as allergic reactions and cardiovascular diseases. Also, some chemical compounds can affect the polymerization of impression materials. Combined gum retraction - the use of threads impregnated with chemicals, the use of dry threads and gels alternately. Surgical gum retraction - using a scalpel or laser - is used for very deep subgingival destruction, when it is impossible to manage with other retraction methods. This retraction method is irreversible. However, despite all this variety of techniques, there is no universal retraction method that would be suitable and used in any clinical cases.

The purpose of the study is that based on the foregoing, we decided to apply it in practice to compare the effectiveness of various methods of retraction of the gingival margin and subsequently develop practical recommendations for the use of the following retraction methods: 1) mechanical retraction using retraction sutures without impregnation; 2) chemical retraction using pastes; 3) combined retraction using threads impregnated with chemical solutions and gels; 4) gum retraction using Teflon tape. To compare these methods

with each other and find out the advantages and disadvantages of each method in similar clinical conditions. Develop indications for each method, recommendations for their use in various clinical conditions.

Material and methods. V issledovanii primimali uchastiye 21 patsiyent s defektami koronkovoy chasti zubov i zubnykh ryadov, kotorym neobkhodimo bylo protezirovaniye nes"yemnymi zubnymi protezami, v vozraste ot 25 do 55 let. Dannym patsiyentam byli izgotovleny metallokeramicheskiye mostovidnyye protezy i odinochnyye koronki, a takzhe bezmetallovyye konstruksii, takiye kak viniry, vkladki, koronki. We examined 67 prepared teeth. After preparing the teeth for all patients, temporary structures were made and fixed with temporary cement. Impressions were taken a week after tooth preparation using A-silicone material. Before taking impressions, the depth of the periodontal sulcus was examined with a periodontal probe around each tooth at four points, from the final preparation line to the bottom of the periodontal sulcus. In the 1st group of patients there were no periodontal diseases and no periodontal pockets were noted. The depth of the periodontal sulcus was no more than 0.5 mm. In group 1, Teflon tape was used for gum retraction. Two-layer, two-stage impressions were taken. In group 2, the depth of the periodontal pockets was at least 2 mm; the retraction method using pastes was used. The use of retraction paste does not cause trauma to the gum tissue, unlike other retraction methods, and is considered the most gentle method of retraction. We used Traxodent and Aluminosil pastes. Also made two-layer, two-stage impressions. In group 3, the depth of periodontal pockets ranged from 2-4 mm. Retraction was applied mechanically using retraction threads not impregnated with a chemical solution. A retraction thread from the Ultrapak company was used. Two-layer, two-stage impressions were taken. Group B 4 identified periodontal pockets with a depth of more than 4 mm. In this group, we used a combined method of retraction of the gingival margin using retraction cords using Traxodent and Aluminosil pastes. We used

Sure cord threads in two sizes. A thin thread promotes opening of the subgingival zone, and an impregnated thread promotes gum hemostasis. The second thread was removed before taking impressions. Two-layer, two-stage impressions were made.

Results and discussion.

Studies conducted in group 1 gave positive results. In patients of this group, instead of a retraction thread, we used Teflon tape, since Teflon tape is more easily packed into a shallow groove and, due to its plasticity, adapts well to a shallow groove and creates conditions for further flow of the correction layer into the groove. But unlike retraction threads, Teflon tape cannot be impregnated with hemostatic solutions, which can be considered a disadvantage of this retraction technique. Gum retraction in the 2nd group of patients gave satisfactory results, gum retraction was carried out with pastes - Alumosil (Alumosil) and Traxodent (Traxodent), however, the result was worse than in the group where we used additional retraction with the same pastes a thread. Unlike retraction cords, gum retraction with pastes causes minimal trauma to the periodontal junction. We performed gum retraction in the 3rd group of patients with retraction threads. Although this technique gives good results, there is also a drawback to this method. Mechanical gum retraction using retraction cords (not impregnated with a chemical solution) can cause severe traumatic effects on soft tissue. Especially with an unpronounced dentogingival sulcus, as well as in such patients, it is very difficult to pack the thread into the sulcus. The results of the study in the 4th group showed that in the presence of pronounced periodontal pockets, the best method of retraction is the technique of several threads, since the technique of one thread in this case would not be sufficient for gum retraction and, therefore, when taking impressions it would not be possible to remove subgingival area (beyond the ledge space). This would lead to poor fit of future crowns and bridges. When using this technique in patients, we used Retragel, which contains aluminum chloride and other vasoconstrictor and antiseptic components, to impregnate the second thread. The use of gels is most universal, since they do not leak from the sulcus and provide more reliable hemostasis. Therefore, we can say that it

is advisable to use gels for chemical retraction. Despite the fact that aluminum chloride is inferior in hemostatic effect to epinephrine, its effect in this case was sufficient. Unlike epinephrine, aluminum chloride does not cause an increase in blood pressure, which was very important for us.

Conclusion.

As a result of the research, we can draw the following conclusions: mechanical retraction of the gums with retraction threads, compared to other methods, is a rather traumatic method. However, the use of this retraction method is most safe in patients with periodontitis of varying degrees of severity. Combined gum retraction with retraction cords impregnated with chemicals (Traxodent, Retragel, with aluminum chloride) is selected individually, since each hemostatic agent has its own characteristics, indications and contraindications, however, the use of gels with vasoconstrictor properties helps to more easily achieve high-quality retraction and dryness of the gingival area while taking the impression. Gum retraction with Teflon tape gives good results with shallow periodontal sulcus, due to the easy adaptation of the material to the topography of the preparation area. However, the retraction procedure itself was more labor-intensive than when using retraction ties and gels.

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